

Evaluation of Stress Among Females Age Group (18 - 25) Years

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Abstract:- Stress is our response to events that affect our physical, emotional, and psychological functioning. Stressful situations produce a feeling of anxiety, depression, anger, frustration, and their feelings are usually associated with physical changes. The prevalence of stress was 36% in India. This study was conducted to assess bronchial asthma among females age group (18 - 25) years at Sree Ramakrishna Medical College of Naturopathy and Yogic Sciences and Hospital, Kulasekharam, Tamil Nadu, India. Verbal consent was taken from the females by explaining the purpose of the study. The total number of study respondents was 30. The questionnaire contains 30 questions. The parameters of the questionnaire included Mental changes, Gastrointestinal discomforts, Habits, Addiction, and Urogenital discomforts. This study shows that everyone has the habit of taking bath daily and wearing washed clothes and their habits show satisfaction. But, they have a lack of interest, mood changes, and lack of decision-making, also they have irritation, depression, anxiety, and stress at work. Therefore, females need more awareness about mental health and the ability to manage their stress.

Keywords:- Gastrointestinal Discomfort, Mental Changes, Urogenital Discomforts.

I. INTRODUCTION

Stress occurs when one cannot tolerate environmental and social situations. This results in considerable damage to the physical health and mental health of a particular person. Stress affects our physical, emotional, and psychological functioning. Stress can change a person's behavior in addition to physiological, emotional and cognitive changes. Stress is a process that occurs in reaction to situations in our environment termed 'stressors.' So a person with stress can develop eating habits, smoking, Alcoholism and addiction to certain drugs. Stress has several characteristics. Stress situations produce anxiety, depression, anger, and frustration and are usually associated with physical changes. Stress

makes autonomic, motor, and endocrine changes in our bodies.

II. PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

When the stressor is present continuously the stage of resistance will begin, and the body resists the effect of these stressors. At this stage, body hormones play an important line of defense to resist the effect of stressors. The pituitary gland releases the adrenocorticotrophic hormone in the bloodstream through certain cells. The secretion of the adrenocorticotrophic hormone is regulated by the hypothalamus through the corticotropin-releasing factor, this factor reaches the anterior pituitary. The corticotropin-releasing factor secretion induced by stress release ACTH which stimulates glucocorticoid secretion. ACTH stimulates the cells in the outer layer of the adrenal gland. An increase in glucocorticoid level is very essential for survival during stress. It provides high resistance to the body against stress. In spite of increased cortisol secretion, ACTH under the stimulation of the hypo thalamo pituitary adrenocortical axis remains high. Cortisol promotes the formation of glucose, which breaks down fat and protein. This may result in few productions of WBC. Prolonged elevation of cortisol increases blood pressure.

III. RESULT

The respondents were between the age group of (18 - 22) years. The total number of female students is n=30. Table 1 shows, mental changes during stress. Have disturbed sleep 4(46.66%) and do not have the symptom 16(53.33%). Dreams during sleep 24(80%) and 6(20%) do not have dreams during sleep. Feels frustrated 15(50%) and 15(50%) do not feels frustrated.

S. NO	CONTENTS	YES(%)	NO(%)
1	Disturbed sleep	4(46.66%)	16(53.33%)
2	Dreams during sleep	24(80%)	6(20%)
3	Feels frustrated	15(50%)	15(50%)
4	Lack of Interest	11(36.66%)	19(63.33%)
5	Have mood changes	19(63.33%)	11(36.66%)
6	Lack of decision making	21(70%)	9(30%)
7	Stress at work	19(63.33%)	11(36.66%)
8	Irritation, depression, anxiety	13(43.33%)	17(56.66%)
9	Have hallucination	11(36.66%)	19(63.33%)

TABLE 1 Mental changes during Stress

Have a lack of interest 11(36.66%) and 19(63.33%) do not have a lack of interest. Have mood changes 19(63.33%) and 11(36.66%) do not have mood changes. a lack of decision-making 21(70%) and 9(30%) do not have a lack of decision-making. Have stress at work 19(63.33%) and 11(36.66%) do not have stress at work. Have irritation, depression, or anxiety 13(43.33%) and 17(56.66%) do not have irritation, depression, or anxiety. Have hallucination 11(36.66%) and 19(63.33%) do not have hallucination.

S.NO	CONTENTS	YES(%)	NO(%)
1	Have a habit of eating junk food	25(83.33%)	5(16.66%)
2	Have loss of appetite	7(23.33%)	23(76.66%)
3	Having regurgitation	5(16.66%)	25(83.33%)
4	Having constipation	8(26.66%)	22(73.33%)
5	Vegetarian diet	8(26.66%)	22(73.33%)

TABLE 2 Gastrointestinal discomforts during stress

TABLE 2 shows that have a habit of eating junk food 25(83.33%) and 5(16.66%) do not have a habit of eating junk food. Have loss of appetite 7(23.33%) and 23(76.66%) do not have a loss of appetite. Having regurgitation 5(16.66%) and 25(83.33%) do not have regurgitation. Having constipation 8(26.66%) and 22(73.33%) do not having constipation. Following vegetarian diet 8(26.66%) and 22(73.33%) is not following vegetarian diet.

S.NO	CONTENTS	YES(%)	NO(%)
1	Have regular menstruation	21(70%)	9(30%)
2	Have dysmenorrhoea	13(43.33%)	17(56.66%)
3	Have white discharge	23(76.66%)	7(23.33%)

TABLE 3 Urogenital changes during stress

TABLE 3 shows have regular menstruation 21(70%) and 9(30%) is irregular. Have dysmenorrhoea 13(43.33%) and 17(56.66%) do not have dysmenorrhoea. Have white discharge 23(76.66%) and 7(23.33%) do not have white discharge.

S.NO	CONTENTS	YES(%)	NO(%)
1	Biting nails	7(23.33%)	23(76.66%)
2	Habit of skipping the meals	15(50%)	15(50%)
3	Habit of smoking, alcohol, or any other drug addiction	Nil	30(100%)
4	Habit of exercising daily	23(76.66%)	7(23.33%)
5	2 cups of coffee or tea daily	2(6.66%)	28(93.33%)
6	Habit of taking bath daily	30(100%)	Nil
7	Wearing washed clothes	30(100%)	Nil
8	Medications for stress	3(10%)	27(90%)

TABLE 4 Personal habits

TABLE 4 shows, Biting nails 7(23.33%) and 23(76.66%) do not have the habit of biting nails. The habit of skipping meals 15(50%) and 15(50%) do not skip meals. No one has the habit of smoking, alcohol, or any other drug addiction 30(100%). The habit of exercising daily 23(76.66%) and 7(23.33%) do not have the habit of exercising daily. The Habit of 2 cups of coffee or tea daily 2(6.66%) and 28(93.33%) do not have the habit of 2 cups of coffee or tea daily. Everyone has the habit of taking bath daily and wearing washed clothes 30(100%). Medications for stress 3(10%) and 27(90%) not intake medications.

S.NO	CONTENTS	YES(%)	NO(%)
1	Have headache	11(36.66%)	19(63.33%)
2	Feel tired in the morning	14(46.66%)	16(53.33%)
3	Having sweat a lot	7(23.33%)	23(76.66%)
4	Have palpitation	6(20%)	24(80%)
5	Have breathing difficulty	4(13.33%)	26(86.66%)

TABLE 5 Other symptoms during stress

TABLE 5 shows, the other symptoms, having a headache 11(36.66%) and 19(63.33%) not having a headache. Feel tired in the morning 14(46.66%) and 16(53.33%) did not feel tired in the morning. Having sweat a lot 7(23.33%) and 23(76.66%) do not have a lot of sweat. Have palpitation 6(20%) and 24(80%) not having palpitation. Have breathing difficulty 4(13.33%) and 26(86.66%) do not have breathing difficulty.

IV. DISCUSSION

Everyone has the habit of taking bath daily and wearing washed clothes 30(100%), and 50% of female feels frustrated. Fewer females have lack of interest 11(36.66%), Have mood changes 19(63.33%) and have lack of decision making 21(70%). Mostly have stress at work 19(63.33%) and have irritation, depression, and anxiety 13(43.33%). Have a habit of eating junk food 25(83.33%) and 7(23.33%) have a loss of appetite. Fewer female have dysmenorrhoea 13(43.33%) and

have white discharge 23(76.66%). 50% of a female have the habit of skipping meals. Fewer females have headaches 11(36.66%). No one has the habit of smoking, alcohol, or any other drug addiction 30(100%). Feel tired in the morning 14(46.66%) and 28(93.33%) do not have the habit of 2 cups of coffee or tea daily. The Habit of exercising daily is 23(76.66%).

V. CONCLUSION

This study shows that everyone has the habit of taking bath daily and wearing washed clothes and their habits show satisfaction. But, they have a lack of interest, mood changes, and also a lack of decision-making, also they have irritation, depression, anxiety, and stress at work. Therefore, females need more awareness about mental health and the ability to manage their stress.

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